

THE PRIORITY TASKS OF DEVELOPING THE KNOWLEDGE OF BIOLOGY STUDENTS ABOUT MODERN METHODS OF BIOLOGICAL RESEARCH

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Abstract: In the article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of the knowledge of biology students about modern methods of biological research, the methodology of the development of the knowledge of biology students about modern methods of biological research, the effectiveness of the development of the knowledge of biology students about modern methods of biological research were studied. Also, The priority tasks of developing the knowledge of biology students about modern methods of biological research were analyzed.

Key words: biology, technology, competence, improvement, pedagogical, technological, model, didactic, form, method, tool, evaluation, creative thinking, reflexivity, creativity, pedagogical experiment.

INTRODUCTION. If the purpose of biology is to learn new knowledge about living nature through various studies, the purpose of school biology subjects is to learn the content, ways and means of teaching students about the achievements of biology. In addition, biology teaching methodology is closely related to the sciences of agronomy, medicine, hygiene, philosophy, pedagogy and psychology.

In recent years, in connection with the increased attention to the use of intersubject links in biology education, it is in contact with a number of sciences such as chemistry, physics, and geography.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Studies on the application of electronic educational resources and virtual educational technologies in the teaching of biology subjects in the continuing education system to the methodology of forming the professional competence of future biology teachers L. Ravlovysh, I. Bilous, N.E. Rerry, S.A. Brenner, Y.N. Arbuzova, S.B. Bogomolova, N.P. Stepanova, M.M. Salimova, N.A. Karimova, Z.A. Mardanov, A.K. Rakhimov, J.O. Tolipova; of Bakhodirova researched in his works.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The methodology of teaching biology, similar to that of other subjects, has its own scientific research methods, and the works carried out as a result of the application of these methods contribute to the

development of the methodology of teaching biology as a science. Scientific research methods of biology teaching methodology include the following.

1. Pedagogical observation method. When this method is used, experts - observers study the work experiences of biology teachers working in schools, study the work experiences of the most effective among them, and promote these experiences among teachers.

2. Pedagogical experiment method. This method is used more in scientific research. Researchers create guidelines and develop new plans (for lessons, extracurricular activities) aimed at solving the problems of biology education in schools and test them in biology education in schools. In order to determine the effectiveness of these experiments, which are intended to further improve the content of biology education, experimental control classes are usually separated. Education in the classes selected for the experiment will be conducted based on the new work plan developed by the researchers. In control classes, education is conducted according to the plan drawn up by the teacher. In the experimental and control classes, the same subject is taught on the basis of two different plans, and the learning efficiency of the subject is analyzed in both classes. If the plan drawn up by the scientific researcher in studying the subject has a good effect, the activity of students in studying the subject increases, and their mastery is slightly higher than in the control class, and these results are repeated several times as a result of experiments in other schools, this new work plan will be widely distributed among teachers and introduced into education.

3. Method of psychological observation. Since biology is taught in grades 6-9, as well as in lyceums and colleges, it is studied by students of different ages. Therefore, in order to increase the effectiveness of education, it is necessary to know the mental states of students of different ages, to take into account their personal characteristics, such as their attitudes to biology education, interests, attention, memorization of educational material, and activities. When this method is used, researchers determine students' attitudes towards classes, classes and extracurricular activities. How teachers organize lessons, how they treat students, visual aids they use, how the use of non-traditional education or its elements affects students, causes them to be active or vice versa. , the factors that cause students' indifference, inattention to the lesson, their lack of knowledge acquisition, and the factors that cause students' interest and activity in learning the subject of the lesson are separated and promoted.

It is known that biology is living nature, its origin consists of sciences that study all aspects of the structure, life, and development of living organisms, and

the role of biology education in general education schools is determined by its place and importance in the development of nature and society.

Today's biology is one of the sciences that is developing very quickly and giving birth to new branches among other sciences. Many problems of the development of society of our time are solved on the basis of the achievements of biological sciences. The ever-increasing population of our country requires providing people with enough food, clothing, and shelter. In addition, the impact of humans on nature is increasing, ecological issues are becoming more serious, and biology is of great importance in solving the problems of protecting biological diversity and human health.

For this reason, every middle-educated person living in our time, regardless of his chosen profession or specialty, needs to have a certain amount of knowledge and skills in biology. The people of our modern times are aware of living nature, plants and animals and their body structure, life processes, laws of historical development, the main groups of plants and animals, their importance in nature and in human life, and the right attitude towards nature and its riches. Logically complete knowledge such as being must have qualifications.

Therefore, the subjects of biology taught in general education schools are of great importance in the formation of the above-mentioned necessary knowledge and skills in biology. In this regard, the main tasks of biology education are set for students of biology education of the Republic of Uzbekistan of general secondary education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, based on the State educational standard and curriculum: basic biological concepts, leading g to introduce ideas, scientific evidence, laws, methods of scientific investigation, knowledge related to the formation of the landscape of the organic world; provide information about living nature and the mechanisms of adaptations that have arisen in the course of its development; to equip students with knowledge about the life of organisms, the basic laws of their individual and historical development, biological phenomena and processes at the molecular, cell, organism, population, species levels, to develop their interest and creative abilities in the study of biology, and in the future continuous development preparing the ground for the continuation of the education system; directing students to take care of their own and others' health, to create a healthy lifestyle; guiding students to consciously choose a profession on the basis of ensuring that the content of biology education is firmly connected with current social life and scientific and technical progress; to inculcate in the young generation the virtues of rational attitude to nature and all its riches; Enriching the content of biology

education with materials related to the country, educating students in the spirit of patriotism by introducing them to the biological knowledge of local plant and animal species, breeding achievements, and the works of our great scientists who have lived and created since ancient times. Based on the above tasks, a document-biology subject program will be created, which will determine the minimum level of knowledge to be given in the subject of biology for general education schools. Textbooks are prepared according to the requirements of the program.

Identifying educational goals, i.e. why study biology? The solution of this question, in turn, helps to determine the structure (structure) of this subject, its content, general direction and other problems of education - teaching methodology, forms, material base, and a number of other tasks.

CONCLUSION. Concepts in biological sciences are composed of logically connected morphological, anatomical, physiological, ecological, systematic, phylogenetic, cytological, embryological, genetic, agronomic, hygienic, paleontological concepts. The above-mentioned concepts are in the form of simple, complex, special and general biological concepts. The simple concept reflects the simplest aspects of the structure and life process of plants and animals. One of the important tasks is to distinguish each concept to be studied, to connect it with which concepts, to choose the necessary visual aids and teaching methods for creating concepts. As the teacher prepares for the lesson, he analyzes the issues of how to create new concepts in students according to the requirements of the program and what methods and tools are used to form concepts in the minds of students. Takes into account the possibilities of using intersubject links. In the case of studying issues of morphological content in the lesson, it is required to use practical methods in the leadership, demonstrative methods in anatomical-physiological topics, oral and demonstrative methods in ecological topics.

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